

ISSUES OF ESTABLISHING A SEGMENTAL ACCOUNT IN TRADING ENTERPRISES

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Open access

IJEFI

SJIF 2024: 3.057

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Received: April, 2024

Revised: May, 2024

Accepted: May, 2024

Published: June, 2024

Funding source for publication:
Samarkand branch of Tashkent state
University of Economics

Abstract: The article describes the segmental report as the main part of the management report, the organization of segmental accounts in trade enterprises, and the issues of determining responsibility centers for them. Those responsible for compiling the segment report, the factors important in choosing this report are disclosed.

Key words: segment, account, responsibility center, segmental report, management, digital economy, organization of segmental account.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada segmentar hisobot boshqaruv hisobotining asosiy qismi ekanligi, savdo korxonalarida segmentar hisobni tashkil etish, ular bo'yicha javobgarlik markazlarini belgilash masalalari yoritilgan. Segmentar hisobotni tuzishga mas'ullar, ushbu hisobotini tanlashda muhim bo'lgan omillar ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: segment, hisob, javobgarlik markazi, segmentar hisobot, boshqaruv, raqamli iqtisod, segmentar hisobni tashkil etish.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрен сегментный отчет как основная часть управленческого отчета, организация сегментного учета в торговых предприятиях, а также вопросы определения центров ответственности по ним. Раскрыты ответственные за составление сегментного отчета, факторы, важные при выборе этого отчета.

Ключевые слова: сегмент, учет, центр ответственности, сегментный отчет, менеджмент, цифровая экономика, организация сегментного учета.

INTRODUCTION

The transition to the digital economy and the application of modern acts of trading enterprises impose their own requirements on the formats of segmental reporting, ways to bring them to internal users of information. Today, the transmission of segmental reports only in paper form is losing its relevance, instead it is becoming a tradition to present reports directly on a computer screen in the form of tables, diagrams, graphs of different colors.

Segmental reporting allows you to evaluate the activities of a certain segment of an economic entity and monitor the adoption of various management decisions and their implementation in this segment.[1]

The relevance of the topic. Segmental reporting is organized on the basis of collected information about the internal activities of the organizational parts of the business entities included in the segmental reporting. Segmental reporting in its content is the main part of management reporting and should be conducted in parallel with accounting reporting. And the correct construction of segmental reporting will lead to optimization of performance indicators of responsibility centers, improvement of document management, and profit growth of an economic entity.

The head and accountant of the enterprise are responsible for the preparation of segmental reporting of the enterprise. The head, as general director, accepts reports that are compiled by the centers of responsibility for the budgets of individual indicators, monitors their implementation, and also makes decisions aimed at making adjustments to them, ensuring execution, and provides general guidance on the preparation of a new business plan for the coming periods. The accountant, in turn, compiles segmental reporting of an economic entity based on management accounting data in accordance with the traditions of accounting practice.

When forming a segmental reporting system and implementing reporting, it is necessary to take into account:

- the costs incurred in ensuring the functioning of the system should be less than the coefficient of profit received;
- the system must ensure the confidentiality of information;
- the system should be universal and automated.[2]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the course of the research, methods of a systematic approach, logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation were used. The purpose of the article is to talk about the role of segmental accounting in commercial enterprises, about the correct formulation and improvement of segmental reporting and specific information about problematic situations when providing segmental reporting.

Analyses and main results. In countries with advanced digital economies, the procedure for reporting by segments is regulated by International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) No. 8 “Operating segments”. This standard has been in effect since 1993. In developed countries, there are two types of segments: current (economic) and territorial (geographical). (See table 1).

Table 1

Factors that are important when choosing a segment report

Current segment	Territorial segment
Product and service description	Compliance with economic and political conditions
A feature of the production process	Interconnection of processes carried out in different geographical regions
Type and class of customers, consumers of services	Products territorial proximity of the processes performed
Methods used in the sale of goods and the provision of services	Rules of currency control
The nature of the regulatory environment: banking services, insurance procedures, the nature and payments for utilities, etc.	Upfront risks for the currency
	Other special risks associated with processes performed in a particular area

Article 11 of the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting”, approved on April 13, 2016, states that the head of an economic entity is obliged to organize an internal economic accounting and reporting system, the procedure for controlling business transactions, financial statements for external consumers, taxes and other forms of financial expenses, etc. The procedure for preparing financial statements by segments for external consumers in our republic is regulated by the national Accounting standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 “Accounting Policy and Financial Reporting”, registered with the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 14, 1998 No. 474. [3]

In order for the management and managers of trading enterprises to receive information quickly and make effective management decisions based on it, it is desirable to form independently developed or centrally approved management reports for management accounting.

Management accounting information for individual facilities should be communicated to the relevant managers in real time after each change.[4] For example, for a senior manager responsible for the financial situation of an enterprise, operational information on sudden changes in exchange rates or exchange rates, stock market indices, securities quotations, prices of goods and services should be provided immediately. Managers should also immediately report information about unexpected disruptions in trade, irrational losses and losses that can damage the economy of the enterprise, so that they can promptly take action against them.

Management accounting consists of a complex of different responsibility centers (business segments), taking into account the organizational structure of the enterprise.[5]

In commercial enterprises, it is enough for management segment reports to be submitted by most of them daily or weekly, and some at the end of the month. For example, segmental report data on the number and value of sales is usually provided daily or once a week. It is possible to come to a consensus on the profitability and profitability of individual products on sale only on the basis of data from monthly management reports.[6]

Management reporting on segments organized in this order is compiled by departments belonging to the relevant centers of responsibility of the trading enterprise, according to the following individual indicators (see table 2).

Table 2

Responsibility centers that generate management segmental reporting at retail enterprises

№	Names of departments that are part of the responsibility centers	Compiling the names of segmental management reports that are assigned to manage
1. Head Office center		
1	Management of the enterprise - head office	Summary report on the implementation of the general budget of the enterprise
2. Supply Center		
1	HR Department	* Report on the implementation of the staffing and of staffing and staffing staffing table to the implementation of the staffing table; * Report on the budget of labor costs
2	On the supply department	* Report on budget execution for the supply of labor equipment; * Reporting on budget execution on the subject of labor security; * Report on budget execution for the provision of utilities and other types of services (water, gas, electricity, steam, fuel, transport, etc.)
3. Profit Center		
1	Sales Department	* Sales Volume Budget Execution Report
2	Planning, Economics and Finance Department	* Report on budget execution for goods purchased directly; * Report on the implementation of the intermediate labor and salary budget; * Report on budget execution of direct other sales expenses; * Report on the implementation of the sales cost budget; * Report on the implementation of the sales and management budget;

		<p>* Report on budget execution for other overhead costs for sales;</p> <p>*Report on the implementation of the tax budget;</p> <p>*Report on budget execution of funding sources;</p> <p>*Report on execution of capital and financial investment budget</p>
3	Accounting	<p>*Balance sheet budget execution report;</p> <p>*Report on budget execution by indicators of financial results;</p> <p>* Report on the implementation of the direct investment budget;</p> <p>* Budget performance report on accounts receivable and payable.</p>

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Summing up, it can be said that an extremely important issue is the creation of a system at trade enterprises for the formation and communication to managers of segmental reports on actual costs incurred and results achieved in a short time after the end of the reporting period.

It is also desirable that segmental reports be concise in form and content, optimal, and do not cover too many calculations. The calculations of the existing deviations of the analysis results made in the segmental reports of trading enterprises, the causes and causes, suggestions and recommendations for eliminating these deviations should be clear.

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